

PSYCHOLOGICAL MECHANISMS OF STUDYING THE LEVEL OF SOCIAL ADAPTABILITY OF INTERNAL AFFAIRS EMPLOYEES

Abdrimov Khayrulla Abdullaevich

Independent researcher at Tashkent State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16908012>

Annotation: The process of social adaptation in internal affairs officers is more complex and has its own characteristics than in those of persons working in other fields. The main reason for this is that working in this field is accompanied by constant danger, strong discipline, conflict and emergency situations, and high psychological pressure. A person has to adapt not only to external norms, but also to internal service regulations, a strict hierarchical structure, a system of subordination and a system of social roles. This adaptation, rather than simple conformation, occurs through the conscious formation of a professional identity, the feeling of being an important part of the service system and the readiness to fulfill social roles within this system.

Key words: internal service procedures, styles of dealing with management, team values, professional ethics, violence, injustice, dangerous situations, the need to use force - his emotional endurance, professional identity, personal feelings, initiative, balanced communication.

In the context of professional activity, social adaptation occurs in several directions. First of all, a person adapts to the organizational environment - at this stage, he learns the internal service procedure, methods of interaction with management, team values, professional ethics. In the internal affairs system, this process begins during formal training, training, and practice. However, real adaptation occurs not only through theoretical knowledge, but also during practical experience, in a real environment. Real situations that a person encounters in practical activity - for example, violence, injustice, dangerous situations, the need to use force - depend on his emotional endurance, the ability to make moral decisions, and the ability to act in accordance with social norms. One of the specific aspects of

social adaptation is adaptation to conflicts and stresses in the service environment, that is, the ability of a person to form mechanisms for resisting stress, maintain emotional control, and demonstrate psychological resilience. In most cases, internal affairs officers must keep their emotions under internal control and be able to perform their social roles in a delicate balance. The ability to maintain a balance between personal feelings and official duties is considered one of the most difficult aspects of adaptation. In this case, a sharp contrast between social roles - for example, the need to be strict and demanding in the service, and kind and gentle in the family - causes internal conflicts. Therefore, the social adaptation of an internal affairs officer also depends on his ability to harmonize all his social roles and his personal life. Another important aspect is professional socialization. That is, the employee feels that he is part of this system not only in the service, but throughout his life. This leads to the formation of a sense of professional pride, the assimilation of professional values, and an increase in the level of personal discipline and responsibility. However, at the same time, excessive professional identification can sometimes lead to a loss of individuality, a limitation of critical thinking, and a complete denial of life outside of work. Therefore, a healthy form of adaptation is to operate with a conscious and critical approach to the environment, maintaining a balance between professional and personal life.

For internal affairs officers, social adaptation is a dynamic process that occurs not only at the stage of entering the service, but also continuously throughout their professional activity. Each new position, place of service, team or reality requires new adaptation strategies. As a person constantly faces new social tasks in his work, he is forced to renew himself and remobilize his psychological resources. In this regard, social adaptation is one of the important psychological criteria determining the effectiveness of service in the internal affairs system. The adaptation process in professional activity takes place in several stages and levels. At the initial stage, the employee enters the new service environment and begins to perceive the external social environment. At this stage, he gets acquainted with the system of informal and formal relations in the team, the social norms and values adopted in the service,

the internal hierarchy, methods of communication with management and the specific culture of the team. At the next stage, the employee compares himself with this environment, realizes the degree of correspondence between his values, personal position and professional role. At this stage, an internal acceptance or dissatisfaction with the person or the service, conformity or internal conflict may arise.

For social adaptation among internal affairs officers to be successful, a number of important psychological qualities must be developed in the person. These include stress resistance, emotional stability, strong internal motivation, readiness to accept social roles, initiative, and the ability to conduct balanced communication. Social adaptation in professional activities is not limited to just getting used to the external environment, but is determined by the fact that the person shows himself as an active participant, acts with initiative, and not only adapts to the team, but also contributes to its development.

The process of social adaptation in the professional activities of internal affairs officers requires continuity and stability. This process occurs anew at each stage of service, when changing positions, changing teams, or when serving in a new area. Each time it is necessary to get used to new conditions, accept new requirements, and mobilize personal internal resources. Therefore, an internal affairs officer must have developed such skills as readiness for constant psychological adaptation, analysis of the internal situation, self-assessment, and constructive social communication. In addition, the social environment in the internal affairs system is often characterized by strict discipline, formality, high principles of subordination, and restrictions related to security. Therefore, a person working in this system must maintain a balance between his personal feelings, needs, and social roles. This can sometimes lead to internal conflicts, psychological fatigue, or emotional depression. For successful adaptation, psychological support, social and professional rehabilitation, training and correctional work are important during the service. In our opinion, social adaptation in the professional activities of internal affairs officers is a dynamic, multi-stage process that requires psychological preparation, which is based on the conscious integration of the individual with the service environment.

This process takes place at the stages of initial acquaintance, internal assessment, integration and stability and requires repeated formation in each new position or service situation. For successful adaptation, the employee must have developed psychological resources such as emotional stability, stress resistance, internal motivation and reflexive analysis. The employee's adaptation not only to the external system, but also active social participation, initiative and contribution to the enrichment of the service environment are the criteria that determine the level of social adaptation. The formal, discipline-based hierarchical structure of the internal affairs system and high security requirements make maintaining a balance between personal needs and roles even more relevant from a psychological point of view. Therefore, psychological support, professional training, and rehabilitation measures based on constant reflection are crucial in ensuring the stability of social adaptation. Employees with a high level of social adaptation are usually loyal, stable, communicatively successful, and ready for professional growth.

The specific features of social adaptation in internal affairs officers are determined, first of all, by the authoritarian nature of the system in which they operate. Internal affairs bodies are a structure based on strictly centralized management, disciplinary control and subordination, in which each employee is obliged to perform his official duties with accuracy, precision and order. In such an environment, the social adaptation of a person is manifested not only in simple conformation - that is, external conformity, but also in internal psychological acceptance, feeling of being an integral part of the system and the level of readiness to consistently fulfill his social role.

Persons serving in an authoritarian structure are located in a strict hierarchical system, which determines their duties, responsibilities, powers and mutual relations in the service. In such a system, top-down management is dominant, decisions are made mainly from the center, and execution is carried out in a strict order. Therefore, the social adaptation of an internal affairs officer depends, first of all, on his personal ability to adapt to this management style, a positive attitude towards discipline and a conscious understanding of his social role within this system.

Stability in the social role is especially important in such an authoritarian system. Because in the process of service, the employee always acts as a subject who ensures order, controls, and protects the rule of law. In order to constantly and stably fulfill this role, a person must have a specific internal motivation, legal awareness, professional pride, personal responsibility, psychological stability, and moral support. Otherwise, he will find himself in a conflict between his role and personal needs and this situation will disrupt the adaptation process.

At the same time, the social role in an authoritarian system is usually under constant social control. Employees' activities are constantly under the scrutiny of internal audits, management oversight, legal and public requirements. This requires mental toughness, emotional self-control, a high level of responsibility and psychological immunity to external influences to maintain stability in a person's social role.

Stability in a social role is determined not only by the external appearance, but also by the extent to which a person has realized this role in his inner spiritual world, turning it into his life position. If an internal affairs officer cannot balance his role in the service and his position in his personal life, this will ultimately lead to internal conflicts, loss of motivation, psychological exhaustion and separation from professional activity. Therefore, stability in a social role depends on the depth of professional identification, the harmony of personal values with service values and the level of internal psychological preparation.

For successful social adaptation in an authoritarian system, an employee needs not only strict discipline and obedience to orders, but also the ability to consciously, responsibly and consistently fulfill social roles. In this case, a person performs his duties in the service not based on external compulsion, but on internal conviction, social necessity and professional confidence. This strengthens his self-confidence, forms a positive attitude towards the service, and ensures a stable social environment in the team.

In our opinion, the process of social adaptation of internal affairs officers is inextricably linked to the fact that their service activities are organized in an

authoritarian system, which requires the individual not only to comply with external discipline, but also to internal psychological acceptance. The ability of a person to feel free in a system with a strict hierarchy, to understand his role and perform it consistently are important factors that ensure the successful course of adaptation. In this case, the employee must have internal motivation, psychological stability, professional pride and a willingness to consciously perform social roles. Otherwise, conflicts arise between personal needs and service requirements, which leads to psychological fatigue, loss of motivation and even withdrawal from professional activity. The most stable form of social adaptation is the harmony of a person's role in the service with his values in life, and to act on the basis of internal beliefs. An employee working under constant control, internal service assessments and public pressure must have mental endurance, self-control and a sense of responsibility. Therefore, social adaptation in the internal affairs system occurs not only through adaptation to the external environment, but also through the conscious adoption of personal identity, internal stability and professional ethics.

S.B.Kilicheva in her study deeply analyzes the socio-psychological aspects of stress resistance in internal affairs employees. She connects stress resistance with the emotional stability of the individual, self-control, attitude to social support systems and psychological defense mechanisms. In the study, the ability of employees to withstand stress is considered as a factor ensuring their efficiency and health in the service. Kilicheva is based on psychometric indicators that determine the methods of entering into social relationships, moral values and personal priorities of employees in stressful situations. It proves, based on practical observations, that employees with low stress tolerance are more likely to experience depression, emotional exhaustion, and conflict. On this basis, the need for individualized psychoprophylaxis and psychological assistance programs is justified.

In the dissertation work of F.F.Akhmedov on the topic “Formation of socio-psychological competence in employees of internal affairs bodies”, it is proven that the formation of socio-psychological competence is dynamic in nature, depending on work experience, due to the development of the level of knowledge that reflects

the ability of employees to analyze their working world and establish emotional communication with them in interpersonal relationships, ensure psychological contact with colleagues, overcome psychological obstacles encountered in professional activities, correctly solve their professional tasks, correctly assess the situation and analyze information.

In our conclusion, the main factors determining the psychological characteristics of social adaptation in internal affairs officers are professional motivation, psychological stability, professional competence and stress tolerance. These indicators are directly related not only to the success of employees in the service, but also to their integration into the social environment, emotional management and self-awareness. The existence of a significant difference between the goals of an internal affairs officer upon entering the service and the motivational orientations that are subsequently formed in professional activities indicates the need for psychological planning of social adaptation strategies. At the same time, individual characteristics of employees performing operational tasks, such as impulsivity, reflection, caution and empathy, form their ability to adapt to rapidly changing conditions. Professional competence includes not only knowledge, but also social intelligence, self-control, situation analysis and the ability to properly establish interpersonal communication. In addition, practical observations have proven that employees with a low level of stress stability may experience emotional exhaustion, loss of interest in service and an increased tendency to internal conflicts. Therefore, for the stable and consistent formation of social adaptation, planned psycho-social activities based on individual psycho-prophylactic work, psychological training and methodological approaches are of great importance.

REFERENCES:

1. Qilicheva S. B. "Ichki ishlar xodimlarida stressga barqarorlikning ijtimoiy-psixologik xususiyatlari" mavzusidagi dissertatsiya ishi. - Toshkent., 2024

2. Выготский Л.С. Избранные психологические исследования: Мышление и речь. М.: АПН РСФСР, 1956

3. Якобсон П. М. (2005). Психологические проблемы мотивации человека [Психологичесал проблемс оф хуманъс мотиватион].

4. Axmedov F.F. “Ichki ishlar organlari xodimlarida ijtimoiy-psixologik kompetenligining shakllanishi” mavzusidagi dissertatsiya ishi. - Buxoro., 2024